

Instructional Strategy and Mathematics Ability as Determinants of Students' Performance in Acid-Base Titration in Obio-Akpor Local Government, Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of instructional strategies and mathematical ability on students' performance in the Chemistry concept of Acid-Base Titration. Specifically, the study examined differences in performance among students taught Acid-Base Titration using Virtual laboratory instruction, Physical laboratory instruction, and the Expository method. It further explored the influence of Mathematics ability (high, average, low) on students' performance. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The study employed the quasi-experimental, pretest-posttest, non-equivalent control group design. A sample of 128 SS3 students from public senior secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria, was selected for the study. Two validated researcher-constructed instruments, titled Acid-Base Titration Performance Test and Titration Basic Mathematics Test, were used to obtain data for the study. The Kuder Richardson 21 formula was used to obtain reliability coefficients of 0.87 and 0.91 for the Acid-Base Titration Performance Test and Titration Basic Mathematics Test, respectively. For data analysis, the research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while Analysis of Covariance and Partial Eta squared were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that the Expository method significantly enhanced students' performance in Acid-Base Titration concept more than Virtual and Physical laboratory instructions. A significant difference was discovered among students of high, average, and low Mathematics abilities in their performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration, in favour of the students with high Mathematics ability. Also, the interaction of instructional strategy and Mathematics ability on students' performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration was not statistically significant. The study recommended that Chemistry teachers should make use of the expository method along with the Physical laboratory instruction when teaching difficult Chemistry concepts, such as Acid-Base Titration, and also provide additional support in Mathematics to students with low Mathematics ability to improve their learning outcomes in Chemistry concepts.

Keywords: Chemistry, Acid-Base Titration, Physical Laboratory, Virtual Laboratory, Mathematical Ability.

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Introduction

Chemistry involves the study of how substances interact and transform, often accompanied by energy changes resulting from the rearrangement of atoms and particles. In secondary schools, Chemistry plays a vital role in building scientific literacy and preparing students for professional careers. For students, particularly those aspiring to careers in science and education, the subject requires both theoretical knowledge and practical laboratory experience to foster problem-solving skills, critical thinking, and a deeper appreciation of scientific concepts (Enneking et al., 2019). In Nigeria, the persistent poor performance of students in Chemistry and other science subjects has raised concerns among educators, policymakers, and parents. Several factors contribute to this problem, including ineffective teaching methods, inadequate instructional materials, insufficient laboratory facilities, and a shortage of qualified teachers (Taiwo, 2020). Salame et al. (2022) reported that students often rely on rote learning in titration, recommending instructional methods that link symbolic, macroscopic, and microscopic representations. To address these challenges, scholars such as Nwobasi and Nwani (2020) emphasize the adoption of innovative instructional strategies and the integration of modern teaching resources to make Chemistry more engaging and effective.

Physical laboratories have long been central to Chemistry education, offering hands-on opportunities to conduct experiments, observe chemical reactions, and apply theoretical principles in practice (Kolil et al., 2020). Practical experiences not only make learning more engaging but also help students understand difficult theories, handle chemicals safely, use laboratory equipment, and think scientifically. Unfortunately, many Nigerian schools lack adequate laboratory facilities and equipment, limiting students' opportunities for hands-on practice. The rise of educational technology, however, has introduced virtual laboratories as a promising alternative. Virtual labs simulate real laboratory experiments through digital platforms, allowing students to conduct experiments remotely and safely (Manyilizu, 2023). They are cost-effective, scalable, and accessible, offering flexibility in learning without the need for specialized equipment or exposure to hazardous chemicals. Davenport et al. (2018) describe virtual laboratories as computer-simulated experiments that link theoretical and practical aspects of learning. These simulations provide interactive experiences that can enhance understanding and retention, though more empirical evidence is needed to establish their effectiveness in Chemistry education.

The integration of technology-based instructional strategies in the teaching of science subjects is attracting the attention of researchers. While the advocacy for the use of

Physical laboratory is still on, Virtual laboratories are also gaining the attention of researchers. Okwara et al. (2019) discovered that the laboratory teaching method significantly enhanced students' achievement in Basic Science. Afyusisye and Gakuba (2022) similarly found that the students taught Volumetric Analysis concept in Chemistry using practicals significantly performed better than the students taught without practicals. In the same vein, Ntawuhiganayo and Nsanganwimana (2022) found that the achievement of students taught Biology using laboratory practical activities was significantly higher than the students taught using the "talk and chalk" method, while Obafemi and Ogbu (2025) found that Laboratory work-based Instruction significantly enhanced students' academic performance in the concept of Oscillatory motion more than the lecture method.

Gambari et al. (2013) and Gambari et al. (2017) showed that virtual laboratories enhanced achievement, retention, and attitudes in both Physics and Chemistry, respectively. Bobson and Obafemi (2025) found that Virtual laboratory-based Instruction significantly enhanced students' performance in Basic Science more than the Field Trip method, while Usman (2021) found that both physical and virtual laboratories significantly improved achievement and retention in Geography compared to lecture method. These findings indicate that while physical laboratories remain irreplaceable, virtual laboratories can complement traditional instruction, especially where resources are scarce. Ndukwe and Obafemi (2023) however, discovered that the guided inquiry method significantly enhanced the performance of students more than a virtual laboratory instruction in the Chemistry concept of Redox Reaction.

Despite its importance, Chemistry is widely regarded as one of the difficult subjects by secondary school students. This perception stems from its mathematical nature. Mathematics is the language

of science, expressed through numbers, symbols, statements, formulas, logic, axioms, proofs, and theorems (George & Charles-Ogan, 2023). Calculations involving equations, formulas, and symbolic representations require strong mathematical ability, which is indispensable for scientific concepts such as stoichiometry, chemical kinetics, gas laws, and quantitative analysis (Schoenfeld, 2014). Weak mathematical foundations may therefore hinder students' ability to solve Chemistry problems accurately and confidently. A sound knowledge of Mathematics is essential for understanding and solving Chemistry problems. The worrisome fact however, is that many secondary school students find Chemistry difficult, largely due to the mathematical calculations embedded in the subject, which are rooted in basic mathematics.

Many students struggle to apply mathematical concepts in Chemistry. As discovered in a study in Physics by Mwangala and Shumba (2016), students have difficulty in the mathematical operations involved in science. These include the inability to correctly apply mathematical principles, the inability to identify and interpret formulas, the inability to use mathematical concepts to create diagrams and graphs, and the inability to extract mathematical information from diagrams and graphs. This is an indication that many students do not possess the knowledge or ability in Mathematics that can enhance their understanding and achievement in quantitative science subjects such as Chemistry. Obafemi (2005) discovered that 90% of students involved in the study lamented that almost all the topics in Physics have several mathematical formulae, many problems cannot be solved without a formula, and someone must be smart and careful not to interchange one formula for another. And this makes the study of Physics cumbersome for them. (Omeodu, 2019) found that only 22.58 % of

respondents had high mathematical competencies, 30.65% had medium mathematical competencies, and 46.77% which is a majority of them, had low mathematical competencies in Physics.

Indicating the importance of mathematics ability in the study of scientific concepts, Umaru and Salau (2019) found that the relationship between students' achievement scores in mathematics and Chemistry was positive and significant. Similarly, Ademoroti and Obafemi (2021) found a significant difference among students of different Mathematics abilities in their performance in Chemistry concepts, in favour of the students with high Mathematics ability. Obafemi and Ogunkunle (2013b) in the same vein, found a significant difference among students with high, average, and low mathematics abilities in their performance in the different teaching strategies used in the study. The students with high mathematics ability had the best performance at the application level in the concept of Sound waves when compared with the students with average and low mathematics abilities. The same result was also found in the students' performance at the analysis level in the concept of Sound waves.

Investigating the interaction of instructional strategy and mathematics ability, Obafemi (2012) found no significant joint effect of instructional strategy and math ability on students' performance at the understanding and analysis levels in the concept of Light waves. Obafemi and Ogunkunle (2013a) similarly found no significant joint effect of math ability and instructional strategy on students' performance at the understanding level in the concept of Sound waves. Obafemi (2012) however, discovered a significant difference in the interaction of instructional strategy and math ability on students' performance at the application level in the concept of Light waves in the same study.

Statement of the Problem

Chemistry is a core science subject vital for careers in science, technology, and medicine. Despite this obvious importance, students' performance in Chemistry in Nigerian secondary schools remains persistently low, particularly in the West African Secondary School Certificate Examination (WASSCE). Concerning the concept of Acid-Base Titration, WAEC Chief Examiner's report for Chemistry in the years 2020 to 2023 listed students' weaknesses of the manipulation of titre values to agree with those of the teachers, which shows poor knowledge of Titration. The reports also indicated that the students demonstrated poor Mathematics skills in the examination. This poor performance threatens students' readiness for science-related careers and hinders national development. Could the poor performance be due to the instructional strategies being used to teach Chemistry? Could the poor performance be due to poor mathematical skill? What is the influence of Mathematics ability on students' performance in Chemistry? This study is therefore aimed at investigating the effect of instructional strategy and mathematics ability on students' performance in the Chemistry concept of Acid-base Titration.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to investigate the effect of instructional strategy and mathematics ability on students' performance in the Chemistry concept of Acid-Base Titration.

The study specifically sought to:

1. investigate the difference among students taught using Virtual laboratory instruction, those taught using Physical laboratory instruction and those taught using Expository method in their performance in Acid-Base Titration.

- ascertain the difference among students of different Mathematics abilities (high, average, low) in their performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration.
- determine the joint effect of instructional strategy and mathematics ability on students' performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- What is the difference among students taught using Virtual laboratory instruction, those taught using Physical laboratory instruction and those taught using Expository method in their performance in Acid-Base Titration?
- What difference exists among students of different Mathematics abilities (high, average, low) in their performance in Acid-Base Titration?
- What is the joint effect of instructional strategy and mathematics ability on students' performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- There is no significant difference among students taught using Virtual laboratory instruction, those taught using Physical laboratory instruction and those taught using Expository method in their performance in Acid-Base Titration.
- There is no significant difference among students of different Mathematics abilities (high, average, low) in their performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration.
- There is no significant joint effect of instructional strategy and mathematics ability on students' performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration.

Materials and Methods

The study employed a quasi-experimental pretest-posttest non-equivalent control group design to investigate the effect of instructional strategy and mathematics ability on students' performance in Acid-base Titration. The population consisted of 3,887 SS3 students in 17 public senior secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria. Simple random sampling was used to select three schools from the Local Government Area for the study. A sample of 128 students (41 male and 87 female) was used in the study. An intact class of Senior Secondary School 3 (SS3) offering science subjects was selected from each of the three schools. The intact classes were then randomly assigned to Virtual Laboratory Instruction (Experimental group 1), Physical Laboratory Instruction (Experimental group 1), and Expository method (Control group).

Two researcher-constructed instruments were used to gather data for the study. They are the Acid-Base Titration Performance Test (ABTPT) and the Titration Basic Mathematics Test (TBMT). Each of the two instruments had two sections – Sections A and B. Section A of each of the instruments was used to obtain the bio-data of the students. Section B of the Acid-Base Titration Performance Test (ABTPT) contained forty (40) multiple-choice questions to measure students' performance in Acid-Base Titration, and each correct question attracted 2.5 marks, totaling up to 100 marks. Also, the Acid-Base Titration Performance Test (ABTPT) contained forty (40) multiple-

choice questions to measure students' ability in mathematics involved in Acid-base Titration. Each correct question attracted 2.5 marks, totaling up to 100 marks. Both instruments were validated by Chemistry teachers, two experts in Science Education, and experts in measurement and evaluation. The instruments were pilot-tested, and the Kuder-Richardson 21 formula was used to obtain the reliability indices of 0.87 and 0.91 for the Acid-Base Titration Performance Test (ABTPT) and the Titration Basic Mathematics Test (TBMT), respectively.

Research assistants (subject teachers) implemented the interventions which lasted for eleven (11) weeks. The students in the experimental group 1 were taught Acid-Base Titration concept of using the Virtual Lab instruction, the students in experimental group 2 were taught the same concept using the Physical Lab instruction, while the students in the control group were taught the same concept using the Expository Method. ABTPT and TBMT were administered to the students in each group as pretest before they were taught, while only the ABTPT was re-administered to them after the teaching as post-test. The students' answers to the pretest and post-test were graded and their scores constituted the data for this study. The students' scores from TBMT were used to determine the mathematics abilities of the students and categorize them into high, average and low mathematics abilities. The research questions were answered using Mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significance level using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and Partial Eta Squared.

Results

Research Questions

Research question 1: What is the difference among students taught using Virtual laboratory instruction, those taught using Physical laboratory instruction and those taught using Expository method in their performance in Acid-Base Titration?

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation Values of Students' Performance Classified by Instructional Strategy

Strategy		Pretest	Posttest	Gain
Virtual Laboratory	Mean	35.6923	50.6308	14.9385
	Std. Deviation	9.5454	12.8529	14.4675
	n	65	65	65
Physical Laboratory	Mean	66.4706	64.5588	-1.9118
	Std. Deviation	10.1339	10.7744	8.8775
	n	34	34	34
Expository Method	Mean	30.1724	56.8897	26.7172
	Std. Deviation	9.6346	14.1995	12.8592
	n	29	29	29

Table 1 presents the mean and standard deviation values of students' performance across different instructional strategies. Students taught using Virtual Laboratory Instruction had the mean gain of 14.94 and a standard deviation of 14.47, the students taught using Physical Laboratory Instruction had the mean gain of -1.91 and a standard deviation of 8.88, while students taught using the Expository method had the mean gain of 26.72 and a standard deviation of 12.86. This result shows that students taught using the Expository method had the highest mean gain, which indicates that the Expository method had the highest effect in enhancing the students' performance in

Acid-Base Titration when compared to Virtual Laboratory Instruction and Physical Laboratory Instruction.

Research question 2: What difference exists among students of different Mathematics abilities (high, average, low) in their performance in Acid-Base Titration?

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation Values of Students' Performance Classified by Mathematics Ability

Mathematics Ability		Pretest	Posttest	Gain
High Ability	Mean	47.7299	60.0575	12.3276
	Std. Deviation	18.0021	12.2473	17.0234
	n	87	87	87
Average Ability	Mean	32.2500	50.2767	18.0267
	Std. Deviation	10.6946	11.5587	15.4336
	n	30	30	30
Low Ability	Mean	30.4545	36.5909	6.1364
	Std. Deviation	6.7840	10.5043	8.6142
	n	11	11	11

Table 2 presents the mean and standard deviation values of students' performance based on Mathematical ability. Students with high mathematics ability had a mean gain of 12.33 and a standard deviation of 17.02, students with average Mathematics ability had a mean gain of 18.03 and a standard deviation of 15.43, while students with low Mathematics ability had a mean gain of 6.14 and a standard deviation of 8.61. This result shows that students with average Mathematics ability had the highest mean gain, indicating that they experienced the highest improvement in performance when compared to students with high and low Mathematics ability.

Research question 3: What is the joint effect of instructional strategy and mathematics ability on students' performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration?

Table 3. Mean and Standard Deviation Values of Students' Performance Classified by Instructional Strategy and Mathematics Ability

Strategy	Mathematics Ability		Pretest	Posttest	Gain
Virtual Laboratory	High Ability	Mean	36.5698	55.2907	18.7209
		Std. Deviation	10.1187	11.8800	14.7637
		n	43	43	43
	Average Ability	Mean	35.8929	44.3571	8.4643
		Std. Deviation	8.4129	9.9139	12.4938
		n	14	14	14
	Low Ability	Mean	30.6250	36.5625	5.9375
		Std. Deviation	7.2887	6.5380	7.1885
		n	8	8	8
Physical Laboratory	High Ability	Mean	66.8939	65.0000	-1.8939
		Std. Deviation	9.9810	10.6250	9.0145
		n	33	33	33
	Average Ability	Mean	52.5000	50.0000	-2.5000
		Std. Deviation	0.0000	0.0000	0.0000
		n	1	1	1
Expository Method	High Ability	Mean	33.8636	63.8636	30.0000
		Std. Deviation	8.8997	11.9040	11.4018

	Average Ability	n	11	11	11
		Mean	27.5000	55.8200	28.3200
		Std. Deviation	10.2208	10.8404	10.6493
	Low Ability	n	15	15	15
		Mean	30.0000	36.6667	6.6667
		Std. Deviation	6.6144	20.0520	13.7690
		n	3	3	3

Table 3 presents the mean and standard deviation values of students' performance classified by instructional strategy and Mathematics ability. Students with high Mathematics ability taught using Expository method had the highest mean gain of 30.00 and a standard deviation of 11.40, followed by students with average Mathematics ability taught using Expository method with the mean gain of 28.32 and a standard deviation of 10.64, while the students with average Mathematics ability taught using Physical Laboratory Instruction had the lowest mean gain of -2.50 and a standard deviation of 0.00. This result indicates that the students with high Mathematics ability taught using the Expository method gained the most and, as such had the best performance in Acid-Base Titration.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference among students taught using Virtual laboratory instruction, those taught using Physical laboratory instruction and those taught using Expository method in their performance in Acid-Base Titration.

Table 4. Summary of Analysis of Covariance of Students' Academic Performance Classified by Instructional Strategy Using Pretest as Covariate

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Posttest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	7052.498 ^a	3	2350.833	16.776	0.000	0.289
Intercept	7631.556	1	7631.556	54.461	0.000	0.305
Pretest	2673.167	1	2673.167	19.077	0.000	0.133
Strategy	1511.109	2	755.554	5.392	0.006	0.080
Error	17375.841	124	140.128			
Total	422238.040	128				
Corrected Total	24428.340	127				

a. R Squared = 0.289 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.271)

Table 4 reveals a value of $F_{2,124} = 5.392$, $p = 0.006$ ($p < 0.05$) for the effect of instructional strategy on students' performance. The partial eta squared value of 0.080 shows that instructional strategy had a moderate effect on students' performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected, indicating that there is a significant difference among students taught using Virtual laboratory instruction, those taught using Physical laboratory instruction and those taught using Expository method in their performance in Acid-Base Titration.

Table 5 shows the Least Significant Difference Post hoc analysis of students' performance classified by instructional strategy. It reveals the highest mean difference of 9.593 and a p-value of 0.055 between the effect of Expository method and Physical laboratory instruction. This indicates that the students taught using Expository method contributed most to the significant difference among the effects of the instructional strategies used on students' performance in Acid-Base Titration.

Table 5. Least Significant Difference Post Hoc Analysis of Students' Performance Classified by Instructional Strategy

Pairwise Comparisons						
Dependent Variable: Posttest						
(I) Strategy	(J) Strategy	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Virtual Laboratory	Physical Laboratory	0.709	4.184	0.866	-7.573	8.991
	Expository Method	-8.884*	2.711	0.001	-14.250	-3.518
Physical Laboratory	Virtual Laboratory	-0.709	4.184	0.866	-8.991	7.573
	Expository Method	-9.593	4.957	0.055	-19.405	0.219
Expository Method	Virtual Laboratory	8.884*	2.711	0.001	3.518	14.250
	Physical Laboratory	9.593	4.957	0.055	-0.219	19.405
Based on estimated marginal means						
*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.						
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).						

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference among students of different Mathematics abilities (high, average, low) in their performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration.

Table 6. Summary of Analysis of Covariance of Students' Academic Performance Classified by Mathematics Ability Using Pretest as Covariate

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Posttest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	8821.063 ^a	3	2940.354	23.361	0.000	0.361
Intercept	26425.195	1	26425.195	209.948	0.000	0.629
Pretest	2270.339	1	2270.339	18.038	0.000	0.127
Mathematics Ability	3279.673	2	1639.837	13.029	0.000	0.174
Error	15607.276	124	125.865			
Total	422238.040	128				
Corrected Total	24428.340	127				

a. R Squared = 0.361 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.346)

Table 6 reveals a value of $F_{2,124} = 13.029$, $p = 0.000$ ($p < 0.05$) for the effect of mathematics ability on students' academic performance. The partial eta squared value of 0.174 shows that mathematics ability had a large effect on students' performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected, indicating that there is a significant difference among students of high, average, and low mathematics abilities in their performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration.

Table 7 presents the Least Significant Difference Post hoc analysis of students' performance classified by mathematics ability. It reveals the highest mean difference of 18.84 and a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$) between the students of high mathematics ability and the students of low Mathematics ability. This indicates that the students of high Mathematics ability contributed most to the significant difference among the students of different Mathematics abilities in their performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration.

Table 7. Least Significant Difference Post Hoc Analysis of Students' Performance Classified by Mathematics Ability

Pairwise Comparisons						
Dependent Variable: Posttest						
(I) Mathematics Ability	(J) Mathematics Ability	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig. ^b	95% Confidence Interval for Difference ^b	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
High Ability	Average Ability	5.635*	2.568	0.030	0.552	10.718
	Low Ability	18.840*	3.752	0.000	11.414	26.265
Average Ability	High Ability	-5.635*	2.568	0.030	-10.718	-0.552
	Low Ability	13.205*	3.956	0.001	5.375	21.035
Low Ability	High Ability	-18.840*	3.752	0.000	-26.265	-11.414
	Average Ability	-13.205*	3.956	0.001	-21.035	-5.375
Based on estimated marginal means						
*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.						
b. Adjustment for multiple comparisons: Least Significant Difference (equivalent to no adjustments).						

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant joint effect of instructional strategy and mathematics ability on students' performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration.

Table 8. Summary of Analysis of Covariance of students' Academic Performance Classified by Instructional Strategy and Mathematics Ability Using Pretest as Covariate

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Posttest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	11143.387 ^a	8	1392.923	12.477	0.000	0.456
Intercept	6473.013	1	6473.013	57.982	0.000	0.328
Pretest	1698.513	1	1698.513	15.214	0.000	0.113
Main Effect						
Strategy	957.358	2	478.679	4.288	0.016	0.067
Mathematics Ability	2694.097	2	1347.049	12.066	0.000	0.169
First Order Interaction						
Methods * Mathematics Ability	359.018	3	119.673	1.072	0.364	0.026
Error	13284.953	119	111.638			
Total	422238.040	128				
Corrected Total	24428.340	127				
a. R Squared = 0.456 (Adjusted R Squared = 0.420)						

Table 8 shows a value of $F_{3,119} = 1.072$, $p = 0.364$ ($p > 0.05$), partial eta squared = 0.026 for the interaction of instructional strategy and mathematics ability on students' performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration. The partial eta squared value of 0.026 shows that instructional strategy had a small effect on students' performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration. The null hypothesis is therefore retained, indicating that there is no significant joint effect of instructional strategy and mathematics ability on students' performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that the Expository method significantly enhanced the students' performance in Acid-Base Titration more than Virtual Laboratory Instruction and Physical Laboratory Instruction. This finding may be because the participants of this study are more familiar with the Expository method, which is one of the instructional methods being used to teach them conventionally. Many public schools' Chemistry teachers do not engage their students in Physical laboratory work until it is close to the time for the West African Secondary School Certificate Examinations. Obviously, such students will not be familiar with Physical laboratory instruction in that short time before the commencement of the examinations.

The findings of the study further revealed that Virtual Laboratory Instruction also enhanced the students' performance in Acid-Base Titration more than Physical Laboratory Instruction. Virtual Laboratory Instruction may have enhanced the students' performance in Acid-Base Titration more than Physical Laboratory Instruction because the students are digital natives who interact with technological devices on a daily basis. As such, they find it easy to navigate the digital space provided by the Virtual Laboratory Instruction. They may have also been familiar with the virtual experience provided by the Virtual Laboratory Instruction, which is not available in the Physical laboratory instruction experience. This finding agrees with the findings of Gambari et al. (2013) and Gambari et al. (2017), who found that virtual laboratories enhanced achievement in Physics and Chemistry. This finding also agrees with the findings of Bobson and Obafemi (2025), who found that Virtual laboratory-based Instruction significantly enhanced students' performance in Basic Science more than the Field Trip method. The finding however, contradicts the finding of Ndukwe and Obafemi (2023), who found that the guided inquiry method significantly enhanced the performance of students more than virtual laboratory instruction in the Chemistry concept of Redox Reaction. The finding of Usman (2021) however showcased the prospect of both physical and virtual laboratories, that both physical and virtual laboratories significantly improved achievement in Geography compared to lecture methods.

The findings of the study also revealed that there was a significant difference among students of high, average, and low Mathematics abilities in their performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration, in favour of the students with high mathematics ability. This finding may be because of the high mathematics ability possessed by the students, which may have helped them to easily understand the concept and solve the mathematical components of it. This finding agrees with the finding of Umaru and Salau (2019) who found a positive and significant relationship between students' achievement scores in Mathematics and Chemistry. The finding similarly agrees with the finding of Ademoroti and Obafemi (2021) who found that the students with high mathematics ability significantly performed best among students of different mathematics abilities in Chemistry concepts. In the same vein, the finding is in consonance with the finding of Obafemi and Ogunkunle (2013b) who found that the students with high Mathematics ability significantly had the best performance at the application and analysis levels in the concept of Sound waves when compared with the students with average and low mathematics abilities.

The findings of the study further revealed that students with high Mathematics ability taught using Expository method had the best performance in Acid-Base Titration. However, the interaction of instructional strategy and Mathematics ability on students' performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration was not statistically significant. This

may be because, the students who already have a high Mathematics ability may have found it easier to understand the concept of Acid-Base Titration when they were taught using the Expository method, which they were more familiar with. This finding agrees with the finding of Obafemi (2012), who found no significant joint effect of instructional strategy and Mathematics ability on students' performance at the understanding and analysis levels in the concept of Light waves. The finding is also in consonance with the findings of Obafemi and Ogunkunle (2013a), who found no significant joint effect of mathematics ability and instructional strategy on students' performance at the understanding level in the concept of Sound waves. The finding is however at variance with the finding of Obafemi (2012), who discovered a significant difference in the interaction of instructional strategy and Mathematics ability on students' performance at the application level in the concept of Light waves.

Conclusion

This study investigated the effect of instructional strategy and Mathematics ability on students' performance in the Chemistry concept of Acid-base Titration. The findings of the study revealed that the Expository method significantly enhanced the students' performance in Acid-Base Titration when compared to Virtual Laboratory Instruction and Physical Laboratory Instruction. The study has also shown the importance of sound Mathematics ability in the study of Chemistry, as there was a significant difference among students of high, average, and low Mathematics abilities in their performance in the concept of Acid-Base Titration, in favour of the students with high Mathematics ability. The importance of instructional strategies and the mathematical abilities of the students cannot be overemphasized in the study of Chemistry. The mastery of Chemistry, therefore, depends largely on the instructional strategies employed by teachers and the students' mathematics abilities. Mathematics enables the solving of quantitative Chemistry problems, while effective teaching approaches enhance students' understanding and retention of Chemistry concepts. This will result in better learning outcomes in students and subsequent application of the knowledge of these concepts in real life situations to resolve societal issues.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that:

1. Chemistry teachers should make use of the expository method along with the Physical laboratory instruction when teaching difficult Chemistry concepts such as Acid-Base Titration.
2. Virtual laboratory Instruction should be incorporated into the teaching and learning of Chemistry.
3. Additional support in mathematics should be provided to students with low mathematical ability to improve their learning outcomes in Chemistry.
4. Students should be involved in frequent laboratory work, whether it is with Virtual or Physical laboratory instruction.

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